

Rearrangement in Furyl-2-Keto-Oximes

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Solvolytic rearrangement of tosylates of benzofuryl-2-alkyl(aryl)ketoximes, 3-alkyl (aryl) benzofuryl-2-alkyl ketoximes and 2-substituted (and unsubstituted) benzofuryl-2-alkyl ketoximes with aqueous methanol depends upon their configurations. Tosylates of *syn*-benzofuryl-2-alkyl ketoximes remain unchanged while *syn*-benzofuryl-2-aryl ketoxime tosylates undergo Beckmann rearrangement to yield benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid anilides. *anti*-Benzofuryl-2-alkyl (aryl) ketoximes afford three types of compounds, namely, (a) coumaran-2-one, (b) chromonols and (c) neutral products which are mixtures of diastereoisomers and assigned a chroman-3-one (and not a chroman-4-one) structure.

In course of synthesis of aminofuran derivatives by following the procedure adopted by Neber¹, Vargha *et al*² quite surprisingly obtained *cis*-4,5-dioxo-2-hexenal dimethyl acetal (2) by the solvolysis of the tosylate of furyl-2-methyl ketoxime (1) as in Scheme 1.

Tosylate of (1) Scheme 1

On attempted extension of the investigation^{3,4} with other furyl ketoximes (3) to (9), uniform results were not obtained. Thus, the reaction of tosylate (4) with aqueous alcohol occurred as in Scheme 1, but the tosylates of (3) and (5) remained unchanged while tosylates of aryl ketoximes (6) and (7) underwent Beckmann rearrangement with the formation of the corresponding furan-2-carboxylic acid anilides and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid.

- 3: R = C₂H₅, R' = H 8: R = CH₃
4: R = CH₂OH, R' = H 9: R = C₆H₅
5: R = R' = CH₃
6: R = C₆H₅, R' = H
7: R = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, R' = H

Scheme 2

In the benzofuran series, the solvolysis of tosylates of (8) and (9), however proved even more interesting and the results may be summarised in the Scheme 2.

A neutral product derived from (8) was assigned structure (13) (2-methylchroman-4-one-3-dimethyl acetal) on the basis of analytical data and conversion of its oxime into 2-methylchromonol-3 (12).

Geissman and Armen⁵ re-examined the solvolysis of the tosylates of (8) and (9) and reported the isolation of the same three products including the neutral product which they formulated as (14) from tosylate of (8). The tosylate of (9), however, afforded (15), (16), (17) and (10) including *p*-toluenesulphonic acid but a compound analogous to (14) was not obtained in this case. The conversions are given in Scheme 3.

These authors assigned the structure (14) (2-methyl-2,4-dimethoxychroman-3-one) to the neutral product and disputed the structure (13) assigned to it earlier. Structure (14) was based on the uv data and formation of 2-methylbenzo[*b*]furan-3-carboxylic acid on 48% HBr treatment. The evidence through uv spectrum in favour of chroman-3-one structure is based on the facts that the uv absorption spectrum of the neutral compound was found to bear a very close resemblance to that of *o*-cresol and lacked intense band absorption at λ_{max} 306 nm that characterises *o*-methoxyacetophenone. The oxime of the acetal (neutral product) showed an uv absorption spectrum almost identical with that of

Scheme 3

acetal itself indicating that the carbonyl group is remote from the aromatic nucleus. These workers considered the mechanism given by Vargha *et al*⁸ for the formation of (12) as improbable and put forward a mechanism as shown below.

described in the literature, whereas only (5) and (6) were found to be a mixture of both *syn*- and *anti*-isomers. The isomerisations *anti*→*syn* were effected with hydrogen chloride. The configurations were determined by classical approach i.e. by

In order to explain these differences in the nature of product Vargha^{6,7} pointed out that the geometrical configuration of the oximes could be the determining factor in the course of reaction and they sought to explain these differences accordingly. Thus, they⁹ prepared the *syn*- and *anti*-isomers of ketoximes (1), (3), (5), (6), (8) and (9). Of the two possible isomers of these ketoximes one had been

identification of Beckmann rearrangement products and by careful study of the uv spectrum.

Simple *anti*-furfuryl-2-alkyl ketoximes give single intense absorption band at 270 nm. Furfuryl-2-phenyl ketoxime shows bands at approximately 240 and 270 nm. Only small changes were produced by isomerisation. *syn*-Furfuryl ketoximes were found to

absorb at somewhat shorter wavelength than their *anti*-isomers in agreement with the general rule.

syn-Furyl ketoximes give higher extinction values than the corresponding *anti*-isomers. These differences in extinction value were explained in terms of *S-cis* and *S-trans* conformations. The conjugated double bonds of the mentioned oximes may lie in the same plane either in an *S-cis* or in an *S-trans* conformation. According to Mulliken⁹,

the bands of conjugated double bonds possess higher intensities in *S-trans* positions than in *S-cis* ones. When no steric hindrance exists, the ratio of both conformations of the compound is, in general, equal, although the *S-trans* modification appears to be somewhat more stable. Studies carried out with Stuart-Briegleb⁹ models showed that certain equilibrium may take place between both conformations in the case of *anti*-furylketoximes. *syn*-Furyl isomers, on the contrary, may only exist in an *S-trans* conformation, because of steric hindrance.

The intensity of the absorption bands of *anti*-furyl isomers consisting of both the conformations will range naturally below that of *syn*-furyl compounds of the predominantly *S-trans* conformation.

A reinvestigation⁷ of the solvolysis reaction with the tosylates of *syn*- and *anti*-forms of the above furo-ketoximes separately showed that :

- (i) Tosylates of the *syn*-furyl-alkyl ketoximes remained unchanged or resinified on prolonged heating.
- (ii) Tosylates of the *syn*-furyl-alkyl ketoximes underwent Beckmann rearrangement to yield furan-2-carboxanilide.
- (iii) Tosylates of the *anti*-furyl-alkyl (aryl) ketoximes afforded, in general, acetals of the reactive unsaturated trioxo compounds with opening of the furan ring. An exception to this finding was the tosylate of *anti*-5 - methyl furyl - 2 - methyl ketoxime where levulinic acid was obtained in place of acetal as a result of Beckmann rearrangement.

The conclusions derived by chemical method (from solvolytic experiments) were in agreement with the results of spectroscopic investigations.

In the benzofuran series the configurations of oximes were also studied in the light of pmr spectrum. *syn*- and *anti*-isomers of the ketoximes (19) to (22) were prepared. The pmr spectrum¹² of

- 8 : R = CH₃
 19 : R = C₆H₅
 20 : R = CH₂C₆H₅
 9 : R = C₆H₅

syn-ketoxime (8a) exhibited a singlet at τ 2.14 for the proton at position 3, whereas the same proton appeared at τ 3.00 in *anti*-ketoxime (8b). This may be attributed to the neighbouring group (-OH) effect in *syn*-configuration as illustrated below :

The proton at 3-position in *anti*-ketoxime¹² (9b) appeared at higher field (τ 3.4) probably due to anisotropic effect of phenyl group as a result of rotation round C-C bond. The pmr spectra of *syn*- and *anti*-isomers of the ketoximes (19) and (20) revealed the same pattern. Benson and Pohland¹³ made similar correlations in a series of oximes of substituted dimedones.

Vargha *et al*¹⁰ showed that in the benzofuran series tosylates of *syn*-ketoxime (8) remained unchanged and the rearrangement products as reported^{8,5} earlier were obtained from the *anti*-isomers. The oxime (9) used by Geissman was shown to be a mixture of *syn*- and *anti*-isomers. *anti*-Benzofuryl-2-phenyl ketoxime, m.p. 156° and *syn*-benzofuryl-2-phenyl ketoxime, m.p. 145° were separated from oxime mixture, m.p. 132-33°. The compounds (10) and (17) in addition to TsOH were obtained from the solvolysis of tosylate of *syn*-ketoxime (9), whereas *anti*-tosylates afforded three crystalline products (15), (16) and (18) including NH₄OTs. Vargha *et al* however continued to hold the opinion that the neutral product had a chroman-4-one structure. Vargha's structure* has been adopted in a recently published book¹¹.

Surprisingly, no spectroscopic evidence other than the use of uv spectra was forwarded by any of the two groups of workers to establish the structure of the neutral product. The entire work in the benzofuran series was reinvestigated by Chatterjea *et al*¹⁶ with a view to throwing more light on the nature of the neutral products derived from *anti*-ketoximes.

The neutral product derived from (8) showed carbonyl absorption at 1730 cm⁻¹. The infrared absorption value^{14,15} is too high to be compatible with chroman-4-one structure but is consistent with a chroman-3-one structure. The pmr spectrum accounted not only for the chroman-3-one structure but showed the compound to be a mixture of diastereoisomers. The ratio of diastereoisomers in the mixture (14) estimated on the basis of relative integral values of methyl and methoxyl protons are in the ratio of 56 : 44.

For adoption of structure A or B, the position of signals due to the isolated proton (b) and (d) in the pmr spectrum was of diagnostic value as these are in different magnetic environments. The other protons, namely (a), (c) and (e) in such a situation would be of little value for structural distinction. In structure A, the proton (d) is highly deshielded as

* A different structure suggested by Varga *et al*¹⁰ has come to our notice. Earlier, the structure was considered and discarded by Geissman and Armen⁶.

indeed is the case, τ 5.3 (s, 1H). Further, the proton (d) in B would be expected to be coupled by adjacent protons (b) and *vice-versa*. The protons (b) appear as a singlet at τ 7.6 (s, 3H) when R=H. The pmr spectra of the neutral products (21) to (23) and one isomer of (22) and (23) showed also sharp singlets at about τ 5.3 for the proton (d).

The mass spectra of pure diastereoisomers (22) and (23) is consistent with chroman-3-one structures¹⁶.

TLC also indicated the neutral product from (8) to be a mixture and one diastereoisomer was separated only in pure form by repeated column chromatography (alumina) and homogeneity of the pure isomer determined by pmr spectroscopy. This isomer on oximation afforded a pure oxime, m.p. 156-57° (*vide supra*).

The mixture of oximes (24) from the neutral product (14) was separated into two components having m.p. 156-57° and m.p. 105° (one oxime reported earlier⁹). [Theoretically, each of the postulated diastereoisomers could afford two oximes (*syn* and *anti*) but only one is obtained in practice]. The pmr spectra¹⁶ of both oximes are consistent with a chroman-3-one structure and in agreement with their diastereoisomeric relationship. The new oxime, m.p. 105°, on treatment with dil. H₂SO₄ also rearranged to give 2-methyl-3-hydroxychromone as was previously reported from the oxime, m.p. 156-57°. The yields of 2-methyl-3-hydroxychromone from each of the isomeric oxime were comparable. This transformation was explained in terms of Geissman structure as above (*cf.* Vargha⁹).

Analogous experiments with tosylates of *anti*-benzofuryl-2-ethyl ketoximes (19), benzofuryl-2-benzyl ketoxime (20) and benzofuryl-2-phenyl ketoxime (9) have been carried out by Chatterjea *et al*¹⁶. The tosylates of *anti*-ketoximes (19) and (20) reacted with aqueous methanol in similar way as tosylate of *anti*-benzofuryl-2-methyl ketoxime (8) and afforded similar sets of three products in addition to NH₄OTs. The neutral products may be formulated as (21) to (23).

Neutral products

- 21: R₁ = C₂H₅, R₂ = O
- 22: R₁ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₂ = O
- 23: R₁ = C₆H₅, R₂ = O
- 24: R₁ = CH₂, R₂ = NOH
- 25: R₁ = C₂H₅, R₂ = NOH

The neutral product (21) on treatment with HBr gave 2-ethylbenzo[b]furan-3-carboxylic acid¹⁷. The oxime (25) on rearrangement with dil. H₂SO₄ [afforded 2-ethyl-3-hydroxy chromone, which was

identical with that obtained from solvolysis of tosylate of (19).

In the solvolytic rearrangement¹² of tosylates of 2-substituted (and unsubstituted) benzofuryl-3-methyl ketoximes with aqueous methanol, only Beckmann rearrangement takes place. Further, the isomerisations of these *anti*-isomers to *syn*-forms with hydrogen chloride of 2-substituted (and unsubstituted) benzofuryl-3-alkyl ketoximes have been unsuccessful.

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